

THE ℓ -CAPTURE PROBLEM FOR INERTIAL MOTIONS UNDER INTEGRAL CONSTRAINTS

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Annotation. In this paper, we consider the ℓ -capture problem in a differential game with inertial objects (a pursuer and an evader). These objects have controls that are subject to integral constraints and start with identical initial velocity vectors in Euclidean space. We propose an approach strategy for the pursuer to solve the problem, and we also find a sufficient condition for ℓ -capture. Furthermore, we introduce the concept of a guaranteed time of ℓ -capture. Our strategy is based on Chikrii's method of resolving functions. The pursuer aims to approach the evader at a specific distance, while the evader tries to avoid the ℓ -approach or, if that's not possible, delay the occurrence of the ℓ -approach.

Keywords. Differential game, object, constraint, ℓ -capture, guaranteed time.

Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается задача ℓ -поймки в дифференциальной игре с инерционными объектами (преследователем и убегающим). Эти объекты имеют управляющие системы, которые подчиняются интегральным ограничениям и начинаются с одинаковых векторов начальной скорости в Евклидовом пространстве. Мы предлагаем стратегию подхода преследователя к решению задачи, а также находим достаточное условие ℓ -поймки. Кроме того, мы вводим понятие гарантированного времени ℓ -поймки. Наша стратегия основана на методе разрешения функций Чикрия. Преследователь стремится приблизиться к убегающему на определенное расстояние, в то время как убегающий пытается избежать ℓ -приближения или, если это невозможно, задержать появление ℓ -приближения.

Ключевые слова. Дифференциальная игра, объект, ограничение, ℓ -поймка, гарантированное время.

Annotatsiya. Ushbumaqoladabiz inertial ob'ektlar (quvuvchivaqochuvchi) bilan differentsial o'yinda ℓ -tutish masalasini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Ushbu ob'ektlar boshqaruvlari integral chegaralanish ostida Evklid fazosida bir xil boshlan g'ich tezlik vektorlari bilan harakat qiladi.

Bizmasalanihalqilishuchunquvuvchigayaqinlashishstrategiyasinitaklifqilamiz, shuningdek, ℓ -tutishuchunetarlishartnitopamiz. Bundantashqari, biz ℓ -tutishningkafolatlanganvaqtitushunchasinikiritamiz.

BizningstrategiyamizChikriininghalqiluvchifunksiyalarusuligaasoslangan. Quvuvchiqochuvchigama'lum ℓ masofadayaqinlashishnimaqsadqilibqo'yadi, qochuvchiesa ℓ -yaqinlashishnioldiniolishgaharakatqiladiyoki, agarbuningilojibo'lmasa, ℓ - yaqinlashishningsodirbo'lishinikechiktirishgaurunadi.

Kalit so'zlar. *Differensial o'yin, ob'ekt, chegaralanish, ℓ -tutish, kafolatlangan vaqt.*

The study of differential games was initiated by American mathematician R. Isaacs. His research was published in the form of a monograph [5, p. 340] in 1965, in which a great number of examples were considered, and theoretical questions were only affected. Differential games have been one of the basic research fields since the 1960th and their fundamental results were gained by L.S. Pontryagin [9, p. 551], N.N. Krasovsky [6, p. 520].

The problem for the case of ℓ -approach [8, p. 272] was first studied by Indian mathematician Ramchundra. Analogous effects in the case of geometrical constraint were considered in the works of Pshenichnyi [10, p. 484], Chikrii [3, p. 56], Petrosjan [11, p. 140], Satimov [12, p. 26], Grigorenko [4, p. 20], Azamov [1, p. 38], Azamov and Samatov [2, p. 33], Samatov [13, p. 907-921], Khaidarov [7, p. 574].

Assume that in \square^n , an object \mathbf{X} (the pursuer) with a control u follows another object \mathbf{Y} (the evader) with a control v . Express by x a location of the pursuer and by y that of the evader.

Let their movements be represented by the following equations with initial values

$$\ddot{x} = u, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad \dot{x}(0) = x_1, \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{y} = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad \dot{y}(0) = y_1 \quad (2)$$

correspondingly, where $x, y, u, v \in \square^n$, $n \geq 2$; x_0, y_0 are the initial locations of the objects accordingly and $x_0 \neq y_0$ at $t = 0$; x_1, y_1 are their initial velocity vectors which is supposed $x_1 = y_1$. At the beginning of the game, we assume $|x_0 - y_0| > \ell, \ell > 0$.

The controls u, v are picked as measurable functions $u(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \square^n$ and $v(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \square^n$ respectively, and these functions are involved in fulfilling the integral constraints (shortly, I-constraints)

$$\int_0^t (t-s) |u(s)|^2 ds \leq r_X^2, \quad (3)$$

$$\int_0^t (t-s) |v(s)|^2 ds \leq r_Y^2 \quad (4)$$

correspondingly, where r_X and r_Y are given positive numbers which mean the maximal resource values of the objects. Denote by U_I^ℓ and V_I^ℓ the family of all the measurable functions satisfying (3) and (4) accordingly.

Definition 1. *The measurable function $u(\cdot) \in U_I^\ell$ ($v(\cdot) \in V_I^\ell$) is termed an admissible control of the object \mathbf{X} (of the object \mathbf{Y}) and the pair (U_I^ℓ, V_I^ℓ) of the introduced classes defines a differential game.*

If $u(\cdot) \in U_I^\ell$ and $v(\cdot) \in V_I^\ell$, then by virtue of the equations (1), (2), the triplets $(x_0, x_1, u(\cdot))$, $(y_0, y_1, v(\cdot))$ yield the motion trajectories

$$x(t) = x_0 + x_1 t + \int_0^t (t-s)u(s)ds, \quad (5)$$

$$y(t) = y_0 + y_1 t + \int_0^t (t-s)v(s)ds, \quad (6)$$

of the objects \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{Y} correspondingly.

The main target of the object \mathbf{X} is to approach the object \mathbf{Y} at a distance $\ell > 0$ (ℓ -capture problem), i.e., to achieve the relation

$$|x(\theta) - y(\theta)| \leq \ell \quad (7)$$

at some finite time $\theta > 0$. Whereas the objective of object \mathbf{Y} is to avoid the occurrence of (7) (evasion problem), i.e., to keep the inequality

$$|x(t) - y(t)| > \ell$$

for all $t \geq 0$ or, if it is impossible, to put back the occurrence of (7).

Clearly, for the object \mathbf{X} , control functions depending only on the time $t \geq 0$ are insufficient to solve the ℓ -capture problem and the acceptable types of the controls should be strategies.

Introduce the denotations:

$$z(t) = x(t) - y(t), \quad z_0 = x_0 - y_0, \quad \dot{z}(0) = x_1 - y_1.$$

Then the equations (1) and (2) come to the unique Cauchy’s problem in the form

$$\ddot{z} = u - v, \quad z(0) = z_0, \quad \dot{z}(0) = z_1. \quad (8)$$

Remark 1. *We discuss the differential game (1)-(4) for the case $z_1 = 0$.*

From Remark 1 and (8) will come below as

$$\ddot{z} = u - v, \quad z(0) = z_0, \quad \dot{z}(0) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Definition 2. *Let $r_X > r_Y$. Then in the differential game (1)-(4), we term the function*

$$u(z_0, v) = v + \lambda(z_0, v)(m(z_0, v) - z_0) \quad (1)$$

0)

the approach strategy or the Π_ℓ -strategy for the object X , where

$$\lambda(z_0, v) = \max \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{h^2} \left[h(\delta + 2\langle v, z_0 \rangle) + 2\ell^2 \delta + 2\ell |z_0 \delta + hv| \right] \right\},$$

$m(z_0, v) = -\frac{v - \lambda z_0}{|v - \lambda z_0|} \ell$, $h = |z_0|^2 - \ell^2$, $\delta = r_X^2 - r_Y^2$, and $\langle v, z_0 \rangle$ expresses the scalar product of the vectors v and z_0 in \square^n . [13, p. 907-921]

Lemma 1. If $r_X > r_Y$, then the function (10) is defined, continuous and the equality

$$|u(z_0, v)|^2 = |v|^2 + \delta \lambda(z_0, v) \quad (11)$$

holds during the game.

Definition 3. In the pursuit problem, it is said that the Π_ℓ -strategy (10) guarantees to ℓ -capture the object X on the time interval $[0, T]$ if in the differential game (1)-(4), for every $v(\cdot) \in V_I^\ell$

a) there exists some time moment t^* , $t^* \in [0, T]$ that generates the inequality $|z(t^*)| \leq \ell$;

b) an inclusion $u(z_0, v(\cdot)) \in U_I^\ell$ is satisfied on the time interval $[0, t^*]$.

Here the number T is called a guaranteed pursuit (or ℓ -capture) time.

Consider the following equation

$$1 - \int_0^t (t-s) \lambda(z_0, v(s)) ds = 0. \quad (12)$$

Let's denote the first positive root of (12) by $T = T(z_0, v(\cdot))$, where $v(\cdot)$ is the appropriate control of the evader which satisfies I -constraint (4). The existence and limitation of such a root is shown in the following Theorem 1.

Theorem 1. If $r_X > r_Y$, then the Π_ℓ -strategy (10) guarantees to occur ℓ -capture in the differential game (1)-(4) on the time $T(z_0, v(\cdot))$ satisfying the following inequality

$$T(z_0, v(\cdot)) \leq \frac{|z_0| - \ell}{r_X - r_Y} \sqrt{2}$$

for each control $v(\cdot) \in V_I^\ell$.

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